

SPIRITUAL REFLECTION IN THE POETRY OF ABDULLA ORIPOV

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek adabiyotining zabardast vakillaridan biri Abdulla Oripovning vafotidan so‘ng chop etilgan Abdulla Oripovning “Shoirning tug‘ilishi” to‘plamidan joy olgan “Men yomon ko‘raman”, “G‘o‘za guli” , “Ona qishloq” kabi she‘rlarida inson ruhiyatini va bu ruhda tajassum topuvchi tashqi olam taassurotlarini poetik idrok etilganligi haqida so‘z boradi.

Abstract

In this article, one of the leading representatives of Uzbek literature, Abdulla Oripov, published after his death the works “I Hate You”, “Cotton Flower”, “Mother’s Village” from the collection “The Birth of a Poet” by Abdulla Oripov. Such as they talk about the poetic perception of the human psyche and impressions of the outside world, embodied in this soul.

Аннотация

В этой статье один из ведущих представителей узбекской литературы Абдулла Орипов опубликовал после своей смерти произведения «Я ненавижу тебя», «Цветок хлопка», «Материнское село» из сборника «Рождение поэта» Абдуллы Орипова. Такие как говорят о поэтическом восприятии человеческой психики и впечатлениях от внешнего мира, воплощенных в этой душе.

Tayanch so‘zlar. Odam, tabiat, lirik qahramon, poetik obraz, fikrlash tarzi, ruhiy holati , ijodkor, qalb, go‘zallik, olam.

Key words. Human, nature, lyrical hero, poetic image, way of thinking, mental state, creator, soul, beauty, universe.

Ключевые слова. Человек, природа, лирический герой, поэтический образ, способ мышления, психическое состояние, творец, душа, красота, вселенная.

“Poetry is not the fruit of moderation. It is born in moments of joy, sadness or anger. The mood of the moment of his birth is immediately conveyed to the word. In this you can see the sincerity of the poet-creator. “Sincerity is the blood in the veins of poetry.”¹ “The poet’s poetic skill lies in his ability to harmonize the dark and depressing sides of

¹ M. Qushjonov, S. Meli. Abdulla Oripov. – T.: Ma’naviyat, 2000. -P. 65.

his mental state through white and bright colors.”² Farang philosopher Voltaire says: “Any example of creation testifies to the creator. Nothing can turn me away from this simple axiom.”³ In fact, if you look at it using simple logic, in every created thing, in every discovery, something from the inner world of the creator, way of thinking, character is imprinted. “I hate rude people. Because he can do all sorts of evil. In my short life experience, I have met many black people. The danger of such people is that they try to pull the leg of the person in front and follow him”⁴ Such people are criticized in the poet’s poem “I hate” from the collection “The Birth of a Poet.”

I hate rude people

I don't like rude people.

Proud, proud, arrogant... that's all,

He seems like a little tyrant to me.

But a mature gentleman is a miser,

Thus, the arrogant is the hidden oppressor.

Last night in class he was talking like crazy

Hello today.⁵

Abdulla Oripov's works can be an important source for determining not only Uzbek literature, but also the history, mentality, values, and unique characteristics of the nation.”⁶ “Each image used in the work of Abdulla Oripov is based on artistic and aesthetic factors, such as a philosophical worldview, a comparison of the balance of the world and man, a way of thinking, a creative concept.”⁷ “Abdulla Oripov’s poems are close to the heart with their sincere expression of human experiences”⁸ “Abdullah Oripov brought to the poetry of the 60s a sincere attitude towards people, connecting emotional experiences to social reality, returning from harsh reality to oriental romance, looking into the self and the soul through the attitude towards nature.”⁹ As our wise people say, "Poetry created from the heart directly reaches the hearts and is sealed", these thoughts are written about the poetry of Abdulla Oripov, including in

² Davlatova A. The poetry of Abdulla Oripov is a study of poetic thinking. ": Philil. Scientific doctor... thesis - abstract - Tashkent. 2022.25 p.

³ www.ziyouz.uz

⁴ Abdulla Oripov "The crown of human life", 1981 y. P 35.

⁵ Abdulla Oripov "Birth of the Poet" .- Tashkent: Adabiyot, 2021. - P.106.

⁶ Davlatova A. The poetry of Abdulla Oripov is a study of poetic thinking. ": Philil. Scientific doctor... thesis - abstract - Tashkent. 2022.30 p.

⁷ Davlatova A. The poetry of Abdulla Oripov is a study of poetic thinking. ": Philil. Scientific doctor... thesis - abstract - Tashkent. 2022.31 p.

⁸ I. Ganiyev, N.Afokova. Abdullah Arif's philosophy. - T.: Muharrir, 2021. - B.21.

⁹ Ernazarova G. National thought and its artistic interpretation in 20th century Uzbek poetry. ": Candidate of philological sciences. - Tashkent. 2001. B.132.

the poem "Cotton flower", the inner experiences and mental state of the lyrical hero are suitable for the landscape. described.

Weeding a cotton orchard in the same lunch
In the arms of cotton I met a flower.
Mysterious, the fire engulfed the heart and then,
I suddenly remembered you - flower face.
Remember a year ago?
Did you walk with me through the cotton field?
Seeing the cotton flower, my love
Say the messenger is a flower

In this poem, the poetic image of Gaza served as a means of remembering the feelings and unique moments experienced by the lyrical hero. In the poem, the tone is innate, mysterious, unique, the feeling, the state of mind is also innate and unique. "In poetic verses, aspects of the spiritual world are manifested in imagery created through many artistic elements, especially poetic images. Poetic images become the main factor that unites other elements in revealing the facets of the spiritual world"¹⁰ After all, B.G. As Belinsky noted, "Poetry speaks to the soul with images, and the genesis of images in it is the essence of the expression of beauty, which is reflected in the construction of all physical phenomena and forms of nature."¹¹ "Poetry should speak not in descriptions, but in pictures and images; Poetry does not describe or copy an object, but creates it..."¹² While reading the poem "Mother village", we seem to be involuntarily walking into the world of the village, we feel ourselves in the nature of the village. We enjoy its scenery, our spirit is involuntarily refreshed. After all, Abdulla Oripov was one of the main themes of the creation of the hymn of mother village throughout his life. For him, the nature, vegetation, people, weather of his village - in general, everything was lonely and unique.

My childhood is still before my eyes,
The mountain air inspired me again.
And the valleys are covered,
Navo flutes are close to this heart.
My happy childhood, oh mother village,
I'm with you again.
When I go to my dream
You gave me the go ahead, I keep my word.

¹⁰ Umirzogova N. The image of the spirit in the poetry of Usman Nasir. Candidate of philological sciences - Tashkent. 2005. P 11.

¹¹ Belinsky B.G. Literary dreams. - Tashkent: Literary and Art Publishing House named after Gafur Gulam, 1977. - P. 103-104.

Thanks to poetic mastery, we feel the psyche of the lyrical hero, because the poetry of Abdullar Oripov is infectious and impressive. Everything, the creative lyrical hero embodies in his eyes the emotional experiences associated with his village, childhood memories, an invisible feeling, that is, love, draws him to the village, the only and true wave of emotions in the heart of the lyrical hero. caused the birth of beautiful poetic lines.

In conclusion, Abdulla Oripov said: "The creator must accept universal pain as personal pain or raise personal pain to the level of universal pain"¹³ His words seem to be spoken for today's poetry. It can be noted that in the works of Abdula Oripov, the artistic response to a number of events in social and spiritual life takes an active form. It is known that various events occur in society, to which creative people cannot be indifferent, painful questions of the time worry the creators of this time, and they are aware of the problems of life that are today out of sight of many people. but can concern everyone tomorrow, considers it a commandment of the heart to look into an artistic microscope and illuminate the reality of life in artistic reality.

List of used literature:

1. Belinsky B.G. Literary dreams. - Tashkent: Literary and Art Publishing House named after Gafur Ghulam, 1977. - P. 103-104.
2. Belinsky B.G. Selected works. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1955, 1955. - P213.
3. M. Kushjanov, S. Meli. Abdulla Oripov. - T.: Ma'naviyat, 2000. -P 65.
4. Davlatova Adiba Rakhmatovna "" - a study of poetic thinking in the poetry of Abdulla Oripov. ": Fil. Scientific doctor... dis. - abstract. - Tashkent. 2022.-P 25.
5. I. Ganiyev, N.Afokova. Abdullah Arif's philosophy. - T.: Muharrir, 2021. – P 21.
6. Ernazarova G. National thought and its artistic interpretation in 20th century Uzbek poetry. ": Candidate of philological sciences. - Tashkent. 2001. P132.
7. Umirzokova N. The image of the spirit in the poetry of Usman Nasir. Candidate of philological sciences - Tashkent. 2005. P 11.
8. M. Qushjonov, S. Meli. Abdulla Oripov. – T.: Ma'naviyat, 2000. -P. 65.
9. Davlatova A. The poetry of Abdulla Oripov is a study of poetic thinking : Philil. Scientific doctor... thesis - abstract - Tashkent. 2022. P 25.
10. Abdulla Oripov "The crown of human life", 1981 . P 35.
11. Abdulla Oripov "Birth of the Poet" .- Tashkent: Adabiyot, 2021. - P.106.
12. www.ziyouz.uz

¹³ Abdulla Oripov. A child of need. - Tashkent, 1988. B.117

